

A NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF DRAPING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A numerical study was performed to assess the modelling capabilities and gain understanding of the tensile behavior of three-dimensional (3D) woven layer-to-layer composites incorporating in-plane preform shearing. The as-woven, sheared unit cell geometries generated by a high fidelity digital element model served as the basis to numerically analyse the mechanical material behavior. Two continuum damage material models, able to predict the initiation and progression of the distinctive failure mechanisms, were implemented in a commercial solver to simulate the yarn and pure matrix response, respectively. The finite element simulations were in good agreement with the experimental data and revealed the strong dependence of damage onset location and propagation direction on the internal yarn architecture. A gradual material softening visible on the experimental stress-strain curves was attributed to the accumulation of damage initiating at the early loading stages, while the angle shift of the warp yarns contributed to the increase of the elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength and strain capacity on the weft direction.

1 INTRODUCTION

The upsurge of composites in key industries such as aerospace, automotive and marine resulted in a need for time and cost-effective manufacturing methods. 3D woven composites' ability to produce near net-shape preforms minimises the labor steps, thereby leading to considerable production time and cost reductions. In addition, these materials exhibit desirable mechanical characteristics, such as enhanced out-of-plane properties as well as damage and delamination resistance, compared to unidirectional and two-dimensional (2D) woven laminates [1–3]. The damage tolerance characteristics are mainly ascribed to the effect of binder yarns in delaying delamination cracks, thus letting other failure mechanisms further develop and dissipate energy till complete failure [3].

The unique characteristics of the yarn architecture, however, come at the expense of high material sensitivity to geometric irregularities induced during the forming and consolidation process [4,5]. Yarn undulation or crimp, cross-sectional yarn shape deformation, resin and void pockets, and other localised

defects introduce stress concentrations, and create favorable conditions for the damage initiation [6]. Of interest in this paper are in-plane shear deformations and irregularities arising from draping the preform to conform to a double curvature mold surface. The effect of in-plane shearing on the stiffness and damage behavior of 3D woven fabrics is yet to be adequately understood. The aim of this study is to propose a modeling framework capable of accurately predicting the mechanical behavior of 3D woven composites containing such material irregularities.

2 MODELLING FRAMEWORK

The underlined dependency of the material performance on mesoscopic features of the internal yarn architecture imposes the need to include key details of this length-scale in the mechanical model. Hence, the acquisition of a high-fidelity representation of the deformed, as-woven fabric is of prime importance. Kinematic modelling techniques developed by a number of researchers [5,7–9] have proved their ability to predict manufacturing deformations of 3D weaved textiles offering a good compromise between accuracy and analysis times. For the purpose of this paper, the multi-chain digital element model presented and verified by Green [7], served its purpose in generating the realistic unit cell geometries. The deformed beam element model, as acquired after performing the kinematic simulations, was converted to a surface model and the intra-yarn volume fraction (IYVF) and local material orientations were calculated and assigned on each individual yarn section. The yarn section and pure matrix properties are eventually mapped to a voxelised finite element domain as shown in Fig.1 (b). In order to increase computational efficiency, the periodic nature of the material has been considered. By applying the appropriate constraint equations on the boundaries, material periodicity on the in-plane direction is realised, reducing the solution domain to the minimum representative material volume; the unit cell.

Figure 1: (a) Realistic as-woven unit cell geometry of the pristine 3D woven layer-to-layer material preform as derived from the kinematic model. (b) Discretized unit cell model of the same preform visualizing the intra-yarn fiber volume fraction (IYVF) variation along the yarn length.

2.1 Constitutive material models

Two distinct user-defined material subroutines were developed in Abaqus/Standard implicit solver for the continuum damage mechanics (CDM) model of each constituent.

2.2 Undamaged material response

Regarding the yarn material, since only the individual constituent (fibre and matrix) properties are known beforehand, a simplistic analytical model is utilised to connect the two length-scales. The calculation of the yarn section elastic and strength properties is performed internally within the material subroutine, based on the IYVF, according to the micro-mechanical model proposed by Chamis [10,11]. The constituent material properties used as an input are summarised on Table 1. A 3D orthotropic constitutive law accounting for non-linear shear in the in-plane (12) and through thickness direction (13) is governing the material behavior in the elastic region.

$E_{f,11}$ (GPa)	$E_{f,22} = E_{f,33}$ (GPa)	$G_{f,12} = G_{f,13}$ (GPa)	$G_{f,23}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{f,12}$ $= \nu_{f,13}$	$\nu_{f,23}$	E_m (GPa)	ν_m
276 [12]	20.7 ^a [13]	13.7 ^a [13]	17 ^a [13]	0.20 [11]	0.25 [11]	3 [14]	0.34 [15]

^aEstimates inferred from the IM7/8552 composite laminate properties.

Table 1: Elastic material properties of the two yarn constituents; IM7 carbon fibre and RTM 6 epoxy matrix.

2.3 Yarn damage models

Failure criteria originally developed for unidirectional laminates are implemented to capture the initiation of the yarn failure mechanisms. The onset of damage is assumed to occur when the failure index becomes equal to one ($f = 1$). The material strength properties are obtained on each yarn section by the micromechanical model. On Table 2, the constituent strength properties are presented. A distinction is made between the micro- and macro-mechanical tensile strength of the matrix due to the size effect highlighted by Hobbiebrunken [16]. As thus, the micro-mechanical tensile strength ($X_{m,t}^{micro}$) is considered in the inter-fibre matrix volumes of the yarn, while the macro-mechanical tensile strength ($X_{m,t}^{macro}$) is considered in the neat matrix regions.

$X_{f,t}$ (MPa)	$X_{f,c}$ (MPa)	$X_{m,t}^{macro}$ (MPa)	$X_{m,t}^{micro}$ (MPa)	$X_{m,c}$ (MPa)	S_m (MPa)
5654 [12]	2815 ^a [12]	87 [16]	135 [16]	211 [16]	76.6 [17]

^aDerived using Chamis formulae from composite laminate compressive strength value (1689 MPa at $V_f = 0.6$).

Table 2: Constituent material properties used as an input on the micromechanical model to calculate the strength properties of each yarn section.

2.3.1 Yarn damage initiation

Fibre failure

Fibre failure is described by the maximum stress criterion:

$$f_{ff} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_1}{X_t} = 1, & \sigma_1 \geq 0 \\ \frac{-\sigma_1}{X_c} = 1, & \sigma_1 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where X_t and X_c are provided from the aforementioned micromechanical model.

Matrix Cracking

The prediction of matrix cracking failure follows the formulation described by Pinho [18,19]. This formulation is an extension of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion and is dictated by the three dimensional stress state acting on the fracture plane. The fracture angle φ is defined as the one corresponding to the global maximum of the damage activation function inside the interval $[0, \pi)$.

A quadratic law developed by Catalanotti [20] is used in the case of positive normal traction:

$$f_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_N}{S_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T}\right)^2 + \lambda \left(\frac{\sigma_N}{S_T}\right) \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L}\right) + \kappa \left(\frac{\sigma_N}{S_T}\right) = 1, \quad \sigma_N \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

while the failure onset in the case of compressive loading in the normal traction direction is described by the following equation:

$$f_{mc} = \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T - \mu_T \sigma_N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L - \mu_L \sigma_N} \right)^2 = 1, \sigma_N < 0 \quad (3)$$

The normal (σ_N) and shear (τ_L, τ_T) traction components are calculated by rotating the material stress tensor around the longitudinal/fibre axis as illustrated in Fig. 2 (a). S_L and S_T are the matrix in-plane and transverse shear strengths respectively. The value of S_L is obtained from the micromechanical model, while S_T is calculated as a function of the transverse compressive strength Y_c , and the material fracture angle for pure transverse compression φ_0 (typically around 53°), according to [19] as:

$$S_T = \frac{Y_c}{2 \tan(\varphi_0)} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the friction coefficients μ_T and μ_L , and the parameters κ and λ are derived from the equations below:

$$\mu_T = \frac{1}{\tan(2\varphi_0)} \quad (5)$$

$$\mu_L = S_L \frac{\mu_T}{S_T} \quad (6)$$

$$\kappa = \frac{S_T - Y_T}{S_T Y_T} \quad (7)$$

$$\lambda = 2\mu_L \frac{S_T}{S_L} - \kappa \quad (8)$$

Figure 2: (a) Traction components acting on the fracture plane. (b) Definition of the angles ω and λ . (c) Damage propagation law of the smeared crack model [19].

2.3.2 Yarn damage propagation

A smeared crack approach was implemented for the continuum damage model of both materials. The damage law, after the onset of a certain failure mechanism, is driven by the effective strain (ε_{mat}) calculated from the fracture plane traction components. In the event of fibre failure, the driving strain is equivalent to the strain on the fibre direction $\varepsilon_{mat} = \varepsilon_1$, while in the case of matrix cracking the driving strain is acquired as follows:

$$\gamma_{mat} = |\gamma_T^{el} \cos \lambda + \gamma_L^{el} \sin \lambda| \quad (9)$$

$$\varepsilon_{mat} = \frac{\langle \sigma_N \rangle}{\sigma_N} \varepsilon_N \sin \omega + \gamma_{mat} \cos \omega \quad (10)$$

where ω is the angle of the resultant shear component magnitude of traction (τ_{mat}) to the component (τ_T) and λ is the angle of the resultant magnitude of traction (σ_{mat}) to the shear component magnitude (τ_{mat}) (Fig. 6(a)). The superscript 'el' indicates that only the elastic component of the shear strains on the fracture plane contributes to the damage progression. Accordingly, the driving stress for fibre failure is equivalent to the stress on the fibre direction ($\sigma_{mat} = \sigma_1$), while for matrix cracking failure or pure matrix failure is given by the equation:

$$\sigma_{mat} = \sqrt{\langle \sigma_N \rangle^2 + \tau_T^2 + \tau_L^2} \quad (11)$$

Following the conventions described above, a bilinear damage propagation law is applied to capture damage progression (Fig 2 (c)).

$$d = \max \left\{ 0, \min \left\{ d_{max}, \frac{\varepsilon_{mat}^f (\varepsilon_{mat} - \varepsilon_{mat}^f)}{\varepsilon_{mat} (\varepsilon_{mat}^f - \varepsilon_{mat}^0)} \right\} \right\} \quad (12)$$

The damage parameter (d) is composed as a function of the driving strain on the current time-step (ε_{mat}), and the driving strain on damage initiation (ε_{mat}^0) and complete failure (ε_{mat}^f). In order to avoid numerical instabilities, the maximum value of the damage variable (d_{max}) is limited to 0.99.

To ensure mesh independent energy dissipation during damage progression, the calculation of the driving strain on complete failure (ε_{mat}^f) is derived from the energy absorbed per unit of the crack area (G), divided by the product of the element characteristic length (l_c) and the effective stress on damage initiation (σ_{mat}^0).

$$\varepsilon_{mat}^f = \frac{2G}{\sigma_{mat}^0 l_c} \quad (13)$$

The fracture energy (G) in case of fibre failure was set as equal to the values derived in [21] for a T300/913 laminated composite in tensile ($G_{fft} = 91.6 \text{ N/mm}$) and compressive ($G_{ffc} = 133 \text{ N/mm}$) loading. The derivation of fracture energy associated with matrix cracking is linked to the stress state on the fracture plane. Depending on the traction components acting, the fracture energy (G) can be equivalent to G_N for pure tensile failure, to G_T for pure transverse shear failure and to G_L pure longitudinal shear failure. In case of a complex stress state, an effective fracture energy is considered from the given equation:

$$G = \left[\left\{ \frac{1}{G_N} \left(\frac{\sigma_N^0 \varepsilon_N^0}{\sigma_{mat}^0 \varepsilon_{mat}^0} \right)^2 \right\}^a + \left\{ \frac{1}{G_T} \left(\frac{\tau_T^0 \tau_T^0}{\sigma_{mat}^0 \varepsilon_{mat}^0} \right)^2 \right\}^a + \left\{ \frac{1}{G_L} \left(\frac{\tau_L^0 \tau_L^0}{\sigma_{mat}^0 \varepsilon_{mat}^0} \right)^2 \right\}^a \right]^{-\frac{1}{a}} \quad (14)$$

Accounting for the resemblance of the fracture plane failure modes with mode I and mode II intra-laminar failures, the fracture energy value of each failure mode is assumed to be equal with either mode I or mode II critical energy release rate. The average experimental values measured by Wu [22] on a T300/RTM6-2 laminated composite are used for the mode I and mode II inter-laminar fracture toughness ($G_b = G_{Ic} = 0.216 \text{ N/mm}$ and $G_T = G_L = G_{IIc} = 0.857 \text{ N/mm}$). Due to the lack of mixed mode loading experimental data for the present materials an approximate value of α equal to unity is used.

2.3.3 Yarn material softening

For fibre failure, a degradation scheme affecting all stress components is implemented, which represents the catastrophic behavior of this failure mechanism.

$$\sigma_{ii} \leftarrow (1 - d_{ff})\sigma_{ii}, \quad i = 1,2,3 \quad (15)$$

$$\{\tau_{12}, \tau_{13}, \tau_{23}\} \leftarrow (1 - d_{ff})\{\tau_{12}, \tau_{13}, \tau_{23}\}$$

Regarding the matrix cracking failure, the stress degradation is applied directly on the traction components.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_N &\leftarrow \left(1 - \frac{\langle \sigma_N \rangle}{\sigma_N} d\right) \sigma_N \\ \tau_T &\leftarrow (1 - d)\tau_T \\ \tau_L &\leftarrow (1 - d)\tau_L \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

2.4 Pure matrix damage model

The same formulation as the one presented before for the yarn material has been adapted to describe the damage of the homogenous matrix material. In this case, the fracture angle is perpendicular to the maximum principal stress and damage activation is determined by an appropriate function.

2.4.1 Pure matrix damage initiation

Matrix rich regions enclosed within the yarns are arguably weak spots of 3D woven composites and tend to form cracks at the early loading stages. The formation of such cracks can cause a stress redistribution with a considerable impact on the stress state of the neighboring yarn sections. Therefore, inaccuracies in modelling pure matrix failure can lead to errors when predicting the overall material response.

The paraboloidal yield criterion developed by Tschoegl [23] for polymeric materials is used for initiating damage on the matrix rich regions of the composite. The criterion is considering failure in the general sense, rendering it applicable for the derivation of the yield and fracture surface on the principal stress space (Fig. 3). Performing the necessary mathematical operations, the fracture space in relevance with this study is determined as:

$$f_{pm} = 6J_2 + 2I_1(X_{m,c} - X_{m,t}^{macro}) - 2X_{m,c}X_{m,t}^{macro} = 0 \quad (17)$$

where J_2 is the first invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor and I_1 is the first invariant of the stress tensor. The values for the macro-mechanical tensile and compressive strength are given in Table 2.

Figure 3: Yield (inner) and fracture (outer) paraboloidal surfaces derived from the Tschoegl criterion [23].

2.4.2 Pure matrix damage propagation

The smeared crack approach described for the yarn material has been implemented and the strain components on the fracture plane are again driving the damage variable. An estimated value of 0.2 N/mm has been set as the energy release rate (G_c) of the RTM-6 epoxy system.

2.4.3 Pure matrix material softening

Following the satisfaction of the damage activation function, the stress traction components on the fracture plane are degraded in a similar manner to the one found on matrix cracking failure.

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_N &\leftarrow \left(1 - \frac{\langle \sigma_N \rangle}{\sigma_N} d\right) \sigma_N \\ \tau_T &\leftarrow (1 - d) \tau_T \\ \tau_L &\leftarrow (1 - d) \tau_L\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

2.5 Notable model characteristics

In order to comply with the arguably large time-steps of the implicit solving scheme, the CDM model is adjusted accordingly. A consistent tangent stiffness matrix incorporating the damage law is assembled to improve convergence rate. By implementing a search algorithm to estimate the damage onset point between two consequent time-steps, the need for small time-steps to accurately capture the damage initiation is overcome. This forms an efficient solving approach able to handle the non-linear nature of damage in woven composites.

The model is also capable of simulating the potential unloading of the material assuming a linear stress-strain behavior. Stress relief mechanisms, such as yarn debonding, were observed by Cox [24] to redistribute the stresses of the neighboring yarns, thus holding off the initiation of damage in the yarn section. Hence, considering material unloading is essential to analyse the interaction between the multiple failure mechanisms.

Strain-softening material models, as the CDM model used in this study, are known to induce numerical instabilities. To improve the convergence characteristics of the model, a viscous regularisation model developed by Duvaut and Lions [25] is implemented.

$$\dot{d}_v^{t+1} = \frac{1}{\eta} (d^{t+1} - d_v^{t+1})\tag{18}$$

The viscous parameter (η) is responsible for adding a delay on the progression of the damage variable, which can be beneficial for the high damage rates related with fibre failure and pure matrix failure. A small value for the viscous parameter was selected to avoid spurious model results.

The new regularised damage variable (d_v) can be estimated on the working time-step ($t + 1$) using the backward Euler method as

$$d_v^{t+1} = \frac{\Delta t}{\eta + \Delta t} d^{t+1} + \frac{\eta}{\eta + \Delta t} d_v^t\tag{19}$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Experimental weft loaded tensile tests are performed to verify the numerical model output. A series of 3D woven layer-to-layer coupons were manufactured by the vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) method. The fabric consists of seven layers of 12K weft yarns, six layers of 24K warp yarns and six layers of 24K binder yarns. An intermediate modulus carbon fibre (Hexcel IM7) was the material of choice for all yarns and a mono-component epoxy system (Hexcel RTM-6) was used for the fabric impregnation.

Multiple shear angles (0° , 8° and 16°) were generated by manually shearing the dry preform on a picture-frame testing fixture. Six specimens were cut from the pristine cured preform and seven from each of the sheared preforms with a width set to four unit cells, which equals to 26 mm, and a length of 230 mm. A thickness of 4 mm was measured on the pristine specimens, which increased steadily with the applied shear angle.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A voxelised domain consisting of six- to eight-hundred thousand reduced integration elements was used for all simulations. The stated mesh density provided a reasonable trade-off between simulation time and model accuracy. Comparing the two-dimensional strain distributions from the DIC data with the corresponding numerical results a good agreement can be observed, with the stress concentration locations and magnitudes coinciding well with material spots with low stiffness (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Comparison between the numerical simulation and the experimental data on the longitudinal and transverse strain distribution of the pristine specimen.

The model results are further verified in the elastic domain by obtaining the effective stiffness in the weft direction (E_{yy}) as shown in Fig. 5 (a). Stiffness in the weft direction has clearly benefited from shearing, with the elevated values measured attributed to the contribution of the shifted warp and binder yarns to the weft direction. A reverse relationship is to be expected for the elastic modulus on the warp direction. The model for the pristine case shows a dependence to the mesh density, with a high fidelity

model of around 1 million elements managing an accuracy of 3%, when a 4% difference is observed in the normal mesh density model. This issue originates from the deviations introduced in the representation of the yarns in the voxel domain. Highly compacted slender yarn section areas tend to be underestimated, while the continuation of stress is impeded in highly crimped yarn sections by the saw-tooth yarn element boundary; a characteristic of the voxel discretisation (Fig 5 (b)). Higher mesh densities do overcome in a certain extent these issues by representing the internal architecture in a higher resolution, however, increasing the number of degrees of freedom leads to a disproportionate computational cost of the implicit solver, thus is not a viable solution in damage modelling where a lot of iterations need to be undertaken to acquire the complete material response.

Figure 5: (a) Effective elastic modulus on the weft direction as obtained from the test data and the simulation results. (b) Section cut of a crimped yarn area illustrating the hindrance of stress continuation due to the saw-tooth yarn element boundary.

Material failure was also analysed and a good correlation between the experimental evidence and the model results was established. Transverse matrix cracking and yarn debonding are the first failure mechanisms to develop in all tested coupons and are responsible for the high energy absorption characteristics of the material before complete failure at the initiation of catastrophic failure mechanisms; more specifically fibre rupture. A concave downwards stress-strain curve describes the tensile response in all cases, which is ascribed to the accumulation of damage along the warp and binder yarns and the shearing of the tilted weft yarns in areas of high crimp. The current modelling framework was able to predict the initiation of transverse damage on the yarns and the early material softening response observed in the experimental stress-strain curves. Weft yarn failure in the sections with heightened crimp angle is the last failure mode to occur forming a crack path along the width of the material (Fig.6). Since the weft yarn undulation is induced by the intersection of the binder yarns to the weft yarn path, the material failure surface is happening in a similar angle as the shear angle of the preform.

The aforementioned behavioral pattern means that there is an interrelation between the material fracture area, and consequently the fracture energy absorbed, and the shear angle. This interrelation, along with contribution of shifting the warp and binder yarns, is the main driver behind the increase of the failure stress and strain identified in the sheared coupons. Numerical simulations found to be in line with the experimental data capturing the positive correlation between the failure stress and strain capacity, and the preform shearing magnitude. The validation of the strength properties is yet to be finalised, hence the simulation results for the ultimate strength and strain are to be presented in future publications.

Figure 6: (a) Front and side view of a pristine failed specimen. (b) On the left, the transverse normal stress (σ_2) distribution on the yarns for tensile weft loaded pristine unit cell at the weft damage initiation point. In the detail view, the damage indicator is shown. On the right, the Von Mises stress distribution on the pure matrix regions at the same time frame.

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